

Deliverable D1.1 – Project Management Handbook

Dissemination level: Public

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Declaration: Any work or result described therein is a genuine output of the AtlantECO project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant.

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1 Version History

Version	Authors	Summary of changes	Date
0.1	E. Trabut	Initial draft	07.10.2020
1.0	D. Iudicone	Review for submission	30.11.2020

2 Executive summary

The purpose of the deliverable is to establish the project management processes and structures in place to support the delivery of the AtlantECO project. It is an additional resource to complement the content of the grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement

The document will cover:

- Brief introduction
- The management structures: a summary of the management structure, the roles and responsibilities of consortium bodies and individuals with key management roles.
- The operational procedures: definition of the procedures for monitoring and reporting on progress, the financial management processes,
- Annexe: how to link Zenodo deposits to the AtlantECO project.

This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA) and its Annexes, as well as in the Consortium Agreement (CA).

3 Introduction

The AtlantECO Project aims to study the Atlantic Ocean from pole to pole to determine the structure and function of the Atlantic microbiome in the context of ocean circulation and presence of pollutants to assess 1) its role in driving the dynamics of Atlantic ecosystems at basin and regional scales; 2) its potential of being used as a sensor of ecosystem state and 3) the mechanism by which it drives the provision of ecosystem services.

In order to deliver this, the project builds on four activity streams (AS)

- **AS1: Asses the status of the ecosystem structures, functions, health and services** at regional, basin and all Atlantic scales and provide high quality gridded data products and maps
- **AS2: Enhance knowledge and innovate** by adopting standard optical and genetic observations protocols, cutting-edge network analysis methods and better parametrisation of connectivity and biogeochemical models
- **AS3: Assess drivers and stressors of change and forecast** their impact on tipping points and recovery of ecosystem structures, functions and services and develop eco-socio-economic models to predict their future states
- **AS4: Share and use** capacity and knowledge across the four continents bordering the Atlantic Ocean ensuring a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy and society.

AtlantECO addresses three major challenges **microbiome, plastics and the plastisphere** and **seascape and connectivity** and defines these as the scientific concepts underpinning the Project which, together with their interactions, will help address the gap in current knowledge and understanding on how they affect ecology, biodiversity, sensitivity to climate change and the potential for a sustainable exploitation of Atlantic natural resources. Building on the knowledge acquired about the status and dynamics of the Atlantic ecosystem, an additional challenge will be to optimize a set of tools and metrics to tightly couple ecosystem functioning and socio-economic activities, integrating them in a unified framework with Eco-Socio-Economic analyses and projections, which we consider a prerequisite for the sustainable management of the Atlantic Ocean. A final challenge to be addressed by AtlantECO is the design of a strategy and of procedures to guarantee that the new unified framework will be implemented in a systemic way so that all the components of the implicated societies in countries bordering the basin will contribute to the implementation and will fully benefit from it.

AtlantECO focuses on five ecosystem services:

- **ES1:** Climate support system: carbon drawdown and storage
- **ES2:** Deep ocean life support system: transfer of matter & energy to mesopelagic and seabed ecosystems.
- **ES3:** Food security and the trophic fluxes: fisheries and aquaculture.
- **ES4:** Healthy planet, healthy people: biohazards, cycling of plastics and pollutants
- **ES5:** Biodiversity: resilience, adaptation and contribution to the Bioeconomy, including new chemicals

Within this Framework, the Project brings together 36 beneficiaries from 13 different countries working together to deliver the 55 deliverables and 40 milestones from the 11 work packages. It is therefore essential to define government structures and management processes which enable the success of the project and support a strategy for long-term impact.

While the Grant Agreement describes the requirements and obligations of the beneficiaries towards the funding agency; and the Consortium Agreement further defines processes crucial to the delivery of the project, the project management handbook summarises the structure and processes for project governance.

4 Management structure

4.1 Organigram

AtlantECO is a large project, involving 36 partners with interconnected activities and a multitude of objectives. The beneficiaries recognise the importance of good governance in delivering a successful collaborative research project, and the need for a robust decision-making framework. The partners agree that in the interests of performance efficiency and effective conflict or dispute resolution, a formal mechanism and management structure provides safeguards and arbitration for all parties. The partners have specific technical expertise associated with their own research strengths, and the consortium represents a novel mix of discrete individual scientific knowledge and technical capability.

The partners recognise the need to simultaneously balance scientific and technical effort with appropriate management capability in support of the research objectives, while maintaining performance in line with agreed Milestones and Deliverables. It is for this reason that the consortium organisational structure has been determined by the partners as providing the ideal framework and achieving appropriate rigour and maximising the impact of overall research performance, this is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 AtlantECO organisational structure

4.2 Consortium bodies, roles and responsibilities

4.2.1 Project coordination

SZN, provides the overall coordination of AtlantECO and is in charge of the administrative, legal, financial, and scientific management of the project.

AtlantECO Coordinator, Dr Daniele Iudicone represents the Consortium. He will be responsible for delegation of the Work Packages and the effective overall execution of the work plan. In addition, the Project Co-ordinator will be directly responsible for communication with the European Commission including the provision of all technical, financial and commercial reports.

The coordinator will be supported by the project Manager (PM): Eloïse Trabut and the Financial and Legal Officer (FLO): Giosuè Zurzolo, so as to optimise effective use of research efforts and implementation of rigorous management processes.

The PM will coordinate the activities of the Project Management Team and be responsible for the day to day administration of the project, including communication with all partners and members of the boards, organisation of meetings, collection of reports and preparation of project documentation, performance and progress monitoring.

The FLO will deal with all financial management be responsible for the budget at the project level, liaising with beneficiaries' research offices or management teams, as well as legal aspects including developing, implementing and updating the Consortium Agreement, dealing with changes to the Grant Agreement if required, providing advice on legal and financial matters to the Steering Committee.

The procedures for the Coordinator are described in the Consortium Agreement.

4.2.2 Role of the chairpersons

The chairperson of each management board will be responsible for securing partner consensus on project steering; however, in the case of any dispute between or involving partners, majority voting will prevail with all partners having one vote. More detailed arrangements on representation, quorum, and specific individual responsibilities will be defined in a formal Consortium Agreement that will be signed by all the project partners prior to the start of the project. Through the General Assembly the Chairperson will maintain positive and supportive team motivation, encourage creativity, and ensure that sound problem solving techniques are employed by all parties, and that appropriate and effective corrective actions are taken as necessary.

4.2.3 General Assembly

The GA is the ultimate decision-making body chaired by the Coordinator and comprising senior personnel from each beneficiary creating a powerful leadership team. GA members will consist of one authorized representative per partner, and members of the PMT. The GA will authorise decisions on the scientific orientation of the project (e.g. new major innovations to pursue; lack of progress of one or other WPs or participants). The GA will have responsibility for ensuring that correct procedures are adopted and followed, that all deadlines, milestones, deliverables, and reports are met. The GA will review the technical progress at six-monthly intervals and will agree in detail the forward actions for the next period, and where necessary, any corrective measures to address delays. The GA meetings will include presentations from each of the partners who are actively working during that period. The GA will formally meet at the AtlantECO annual consortium meetings and by videoconferencing in between. However, if urgent matters arise conference calls will be arranged so that any problems are promptly and effectively solved. The operations manager will act as secretary in all meetings of the GA.

The procedures for the General Assembly are described in Article 6.2.1 of the Consortium Agreement and include:

- Members
- Decisions

4.2.4 Role and composition of the Steering Committee (CS)

The Steering Committee, Co-chaired by Linda Amaral-Zettler (NIOZ) and Chris Bowler (CNRS), is composed of the Project Management Team and the Work Package leaders. The SC will be responsible for the overall scientific management of the project and will ensure that the decisions taken by the General Assembly are carried out. The SC will implement a progress monitoring procedure and system, which will have clear timelines for deliverables and progress reporting. The group will meet formally via web/tele-conferencing at least every 3 months to review progress and agree priorities for the following 6 months. The scientific plans will follow the pattern of annual updates for presentation to, and agreement of the GA. At the end of each year the SC will review the plans for the next 12-month period so that a forward scientific plan becomes central to the overall project management. The SC also suggest new directions and monitor progress made in relevant areas of research within the EC and internationally, to be included in the Roadmap in WP10. The WP Leaders will maintain regular informal contact by email and telephone with the participants of their WP and will report problems and solutions arising during the progress of the WP to the PMT. Quarterly progress reports will appear in an annex of the minutes of the SC meeting for electronic distribution.

The procedures for the Steering Committee are described in Article 6.2.2. of the Consortium Agreement and include:

- Members
- Minutes of meeting
- Tasks

4.2.4.1 *Work Package leaders (WP leaders).*

Each WP has two leaders, who are complementary specialists in the corresponding field and who will ensure coordination among WP contributors (in EU, South America and Africa) and the on-time achievement of deliverables and milestones of the WP. The main task of the WP leaders will be to coordinate work by partners active in each WP. The WP leaders will communicate regularly with the Project Coordinator, the PMT and through the Steering Committee by email/phone to report on progress and highlight actual or anticipated problems. Absolute reporting deadlines are anticipated, at this stage, as being quarterly. In cases of important and significant change or deviation from the Project Plan, conference calls with the members of the WP will be organised to take the necessary decisions on the nature and impact of the changes to be made. The WP leaders will be encouraged to share responsibility and to support the researchers of other WPs to participate actively in the organisation of the research, information sharing, international exchange and efforts to promote and encourage young researchers. They will be responsible for bringing all Deliverables and Milestones to the attention of the Coordinator and the Project Management Team at the appropriate time.

4.2.5 **Role and composition of the Project Management Team (PMT)**

To optimise the balance between needs of scientific and technical aspects of the project as distinct from the operational functions of day-to-day management and administration at the project level, AtlantECO will establish the Project Management Team (PMT). The PMT is composed of the coordinator, the Project Operations Manager (Chair), the financial and Legal Officer/Data Protection Officer, The Data manager, the Innovation and Exploitation Manager and the Outreach and Communication Manager; whose individual roles and responsibilities have been defined in section 3.2.1. Together, the PMT will ensure that administrative, operational activities, complemented by project level input for innovation management and outreach/communication management are delivered cohesively and coherently. The PMT will meet on a monthly basis via teleconference, this will be chaired by the Operations Manager who will set agendas and action logs for monitoring. Items will cover project level activities as well as any issues reported by the Steering Committee. Issues requiring major changes to project plans will be formally communicated to the GA. The PMT will be responsible for distributing all reports produced by the project's body as and when required (see schedule in 3.3.1.4).

4.2.5.1 *Innovation and exploitation manager (IM)*

The IM, Alexander Wentzel at SINTEF, will support the consortium in monitoring the project outputs and ensure that partners regularly explore potential opportunities to exploit results arising from AtlantECO. The IM will be responsible for project level innovation management and for supporting individual beneficiaries where internal resources are not available. The IM will participate in all meetings of the SC and ensure that opportunities for innovation and exploitation are considered in all forward project's plans.

4.2.5.2 *Outreach and communication manager (OCM)*

The OCM, to be based at FTO (recruitment December 2020), will be responsible for coordinating the communication and outreach activities with the teams in Europe, South America and Africa. FTO is very experienced in developing and delivering public events designed to inform and engage with the public and in delivering tailored dissemination material for targeted stakeholders to initiate change. The OCM will be responsible for collecting metrics on communication activities and reporting to the SC via the PMT.

4.2.5.3 *Data Manager*

The Data Manager, Stéphane Pesant based at EMBL-EBI, is responsible for coordinating research data management in line with the Data Management Plan to be submitted at M06, February 2021.

4.2.6 **Role and composition of Multi-stakeholder Engagement Forum (MSEF)**

In order to complement the governance structure and support the objectives of AtlantECO, 3 collaboration forums are defined with details of their role, the participants, their commitment and AtlantECO means of access to these stakeholders. Additional members will be added during the implementation phase as needed.

4.2.6.1 *Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)*

The SAB will provide independent advice on the scientific direction of the project. The SAB will hold Annual meetings (web or in person) and provide feedback report sent to PMT prior to each CM. The initial members are: A. Falciatore (CNRS), P. Snelgrove (OFI); P. Cury (IRD) and C. Jolly (OECD).

4.2.6.2 *Industrial and Early Adopter (IEA)*

The IEA is set up to support exchange of knowledge and ideas on applicability of project's outcomes for stakeholders involved in and contributing to the Blue Economy and Blue Growth, they will participate in pitching sessions, be involved in the delivery of AtlantECO case studies and act as multipliers for dissemination. Membership includes: ArcticZymes, CapeBio (CS1), ProOceano, Petrobras, Neoprospecta (CS2), Plastic@Sea (CS3), DEBEERS (CS4), OXFAM (CS5).

The IEA will expand as the stakeholder database is developed over the lifetime of the project, Additional industrial stakeholders will be engaged with as opportunity arise.

4.2.6.3 *Synergies and Complementarities for Blue Growth (BGSC)*

The BGSC will plan and deliver: 1) sharing/integrating of results, 2) joint dissemination, training, communication events and 3) coordinated contribution to standards, policies and Atlantic frameworks. Their involvement and specific activities have been detailed in section 1.3.3 and in the relevant tasks of the WPs they contribute to. The initiatives included are: TRIATLAS, AquaVitae, EuroSea, SUMMER, SIMBA, AANCHOR and iAtlantic. The group will interact with future funded projects that present complementary approaches.

5 Operational procedures

5.1 Progress monitoring

5.1.1 Meetings

5.1.1.1 Schedule of regular meetings

Table I AtlantECO schedule of meetings

Meeting	Frequency	Chair(s)	Attendees
PMT	Monthly (third Monday of each month)- virtual Zoom meeting	E. Trabut (SZN)	PMT members
SC	Quarterly (third Wednesday of every quarter)- virtual Zoom meeting, or in person when coinciding with consortium meeting	L. Amaral Zettler (NIOZ) C. Bowler (CNRS)	SC members
GA	Annual (at least 45 days' notice prior)- in person meeting where coinciding with consortium meeting	D. Iudicone (SZN)	GA members

The procedures applicable to meetings are described in Article 6.1 of the Consortium Agreement. These cover:

- Representation in meetings
- Preparation and organisations of meetings
 - Convening
 - Noticing
 - Sending agenda
 - Adding agenda items
 - Decision making mechanism
- Voting rules and quorum
- Veto rights
- Minutes of meetings

5.1.2 Calendar of deliverables, milestones and reports

YEAR 1												
Month	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Date	Sep-20	Oct-20	Nov-20	Dec-20	Jan-21	Feb-21	Mar-21	Apr-21	May-21	Jun-21	Jul-21	Aug-21
Deliverables			D1.1 D11.1 D11.3 D11.4	D9.1	D11.2 D11.5	D4.1 D9.2 D10.1		D4.8				D1.2 D2.1 D5.1 D10.2
Milestones			MS4 MS5	MS2 MS3	MS1	MS6						MS7 MS8 MS9 MS10 MS11 MS12
Report			I-Q1			I-Q2			I-Q3			I-Q4
YEAR 2												
Month	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Date	Sep-21	Oct-21	Nov-21	Dec-21	Jan-22	Feb-22	Mar-22	Apr-22	May-22	Jun-22	Jul-22	Aug-22
Deliverables						D4.2 D4.5 D6.1						D2.2 D2.4 D5.2 D6.2
Milestones			MS13		MS14	MS15 MS16 MS17 MS21				MS18		MS19 MS20 MS22 MS23 MS24
Report			I-Q5			PR1			I-Q7			I-Q8
YEAR 3												
Month	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36
Date	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	Feb-23	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23	Jul-23	Aug-23
Deliverables						D4.3 D4.6 D5.4 D10.3 D10.5						D4.4 D4.7 D4.9 D7.2
Milestones						MS25 MS26 MS27		MS38				MS29 MS30 MS31 MS32
Reports			I-Q9			I-Q10			I-Q11			PR2
YEAR 4												
Month	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48
Date	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24
Deliverables				D3.1 D3.2 D6.3		D2.6 D6.4 D6.6 D7.1				D8.1 D8.2 D8.3 D8.4 D9.3 D10.8		D2.3 D2.5 D2.7 D4.10 D5.3 D5.5 D6.5 D9.4 D10.4 D10.6 D10.7
Milestones			MS33	MS34		MS35			MS36		MS37 MS38	MS39 MS40
Report			I-Q13			I-Q14			I-Q15			PR3 Final CFS

Figure 2 AtlantECO calendar of deliverables, milestones and reports.

Dn.n: deliverable
MSn: milestone

I-Qn: Internal Quarterly report
PRn: Periodic report

5.2 Reporting

5.2.1 Interim internal reports

The principal scientific partner of each institution will produce a brief internal report each 6 months. The reports will detail general progress and any problems or challenges arising with respect to the work plan. These reports will be sent to the PMT and Project Coordinator in the month following the end of each half-year. The partner reports will be consolidated and distributed to the GA members by the Coordinator and made available for download via the private members’ area of the project website. The reports will contain (1) a management overview; (2) a description of the progress towards the scientific and technological

objectives; (3) identification of challenges and suggested corrective action to be taken; (4) progress towards publications and data depositions.

5.2.2 Continuous, Periodic and Financial reports:

5.2.2.1 Continuous reporting

Guidance on continuous reporting is available in the [H2020 Online Manual](#)

The function is accessed on the Funding and Tender Portal and continuous reporting covers the following topics and activities:

- Summary for publication
- Deliverables
- Milestones
- Risks and mitigation measures
- Dissemination and exploitation of results
- Impact on SMEs
- Open research Data
- Gender

Data will be collected and submitted throughout periods of the project.

5.2.2.2 Periodic reports

Detailed periodic reports will be prepared according to the appropriate requirements using the latest template from the portal and include the following parts:

- Explanation of work and overview of project
- If applicable: Update of exploitation and dissemination plan
- If applicable: Update of data management plan
- If applicable: Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous review(s)
- If applicable: deviations from Annex 1

The LFO will collate summaries of the cost statements and justifications prepared by each participating institution. The explanation of the use of resources will include:

- Direct personnel costs
- If applicable: direct costs of subcontracting (none are foreseen at this stage)
- If applicable: Direct costs of third parties
- If applicable: Direct costs of providing financial support
- Other direct costs

5.2.2.3 Final report:

On completion of the project, a final report will be prepared where results will be assessed against agreed objectives. The report will focus on the economic and social implications of the data obtained. It will also describe the dissemination of the results and the factors associated with their potential economic exploitation.

5.3 Financial management

5.3.1 Payments schedule

Pre-financing: 53.33% of total budget

- Guarantee Fund: 5% of the total budget (released with final payment)
- [First transfer from coordinator to beneficiaries = \(pre-financing\) - \(guarantee fund\)](#)

Interim payment(s):

- Based on costs incurred during the period
- Up to a maximum of 90% of the total budget
- $\text{Interim payment} = (90\% \text{ of total budget}) - (\text{pre-financing} + \text{previous interim payments})$

Final payment

- Remaining part of the eligible costs
- $\text{Balance} = (\text{Final grant amount}) - (\text{pre-financing} + \text{interim payments})$

Figure 3 Illustration of payment schedule in AtlantECO

To enable payments, the LFO has collected the Financial Identification Forms from all beneficiaries. Should this information change during the course of the project, partners should provide new bank details to the LFO by email at: gio@szn.it and copy atlanteco@szn.it.

5.3.2 Financial provisions

Financial provisions are described in Article 7 of the Consortium Agreement and include:

- General principles:
 - Distribution of financial contribution
 - Justifying costs
 - Funding principles
 - Financial risk management and return of excess payment, receipts.
 - Financial consequences of the termination of the participation of a Party
- Budgeting
- Payments
 - Tasks of the coordinator
 - Payment schedule

5.4 Project documentation

5.4.1 Project level records

The Grant Agreement and its annexes are accessible to the project beneficiaries on the Funding and Tender Portal.

The [Annotated Model Grant Agreement](#) which is a key reference document, can be accessed on the Funding and Tender Portal. Always check for the latest version applicable.

In addition, copies of these documents, as well as all other project related confidential documentation, are accessible on the project Google drive to which only beneficiaries have access.

Public documents are deposited in Zenodo and made available on the project website. Zenodo deposits should be linked to the project, this is done as indicated in the Annex.

5.4.2 Project documents

A number of project documents and templates are available for use by the consortium members, these are available on the Google drive and include:

- Branded presentation template
- Agenda and minutes templates
- Report templates
- Deliverable template
- Report form for Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation activities (feeding into continuous reporting)
- Example of timesheet
- Branded Word document.

The library of documents will evolve as the project progresses.

5.5 Project internal Communication

5.5.1 Mailing lists

The project has established a number of mailing lists to facilitate internal communication as follows:

Table 2 AtlantECO mailing lists

Mailing address	Recipients	Access
Atlanteco.general@szn.it	All AtlantECO consortium members	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.general
Atlanteco.admin@szn.it	Administrative, financial and legal contacts	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.admin
Atlanteco.ga@szn.it	General Assembly members	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.ga
Atlanteco.sc@szn.it	Steering Committee members	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.sc
Atlanteco.pmt@szn.it	Project Management Team members	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.pmt
Atlanteco.wp2@szn.it	WP2 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp2
Atlanteco.wp3@szn.it	WP3 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp3
Atlanteco.wp4@szn.it	WP4 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp4
Atlanteco.wp5@szn.it	WP5 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp5
Atlanteco.wp6@szn.it	WP6 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp6
Atlanteco.wp7@szn.it	WP7 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp7
Atlanteco.wp8@szn.it	WP8 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp8
Atlanteco.wp9@szn.it	WP9 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp9
Atlanteco.wp10@szn.it	WP10 contributors	https://lists.szn.it/mailman/listinfo/atlanteco.wp10

atlanteco@szn.it

Project Manager

Not applicable

5.5.2 Internal newsletter

Consortium wide communication is facilitated through the circulation of an internal newsletter “AtlantEcho-Echos of the Atlantic” which is disseminated via the general mailing list twice a month. The Echo provides updates and relevant information on the following topics:

- Highlights of AtlantECO developments and achievements
- News of other relevant activities (for example synergies with other funded initiatives)
- Opportunities that exist for members of the consortium (for example participation in sampling cruises or recruitment and secondment opportunities)
- Calendar of events (activities included are both internal and external to the project activities, for example upcoming workshops, conferences or webinars).
- Reminder and tips (for internal activities, links to resources and reminders of upcoming deadlines).

The Echo is a collaborative process and builds on the information provided by all consortium members who are encouraged to submit content for following issues via a Google form.

5.6 Innovation management

The AtlantECO consortium recognises that collaboration is an important source of innovation. The project management structure is designed to ensure that all partners are actively engaged in the management of the project and that the knowledge gained through participation in AtlantECO has an impact far beyond the project duration. A significant project activity, led by SINTEF (Innovation and Exploitation Manager) will be the development and upkeep of AtlantECO Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (WP10) which is designed to ensure that the partners not only deliver on the overall project objectives but that they also regularly explore potential opportunities arising from the project results; including scientific outputs, protocols and approaches as well as de-novo knowledge. These plans will be reviewed on an annual basis by the AtlantECO GA to ensure relevance to end users. To maximise the innovation opportunities arising several processes and practices are included in the plans for dissemination and use of project results. These include: Prepublication assessment of results to ensure management of dissemination, Regular discussions at consortium meetings on the vision for impact and innovation, Assessment of market opportunities for the new knowledge created by the project ; Development of concrete exploitation plans enabling agreements between consortium partners and with other organisations to pave the way for innovation and exploitation, including the development of roadmaps in collaboration with service providers, policy makers and researchers in WP10. This customised approach will ensure that the project results are successfully transferred and that there is a demonstrated impact as a result of the project. The impact assessment will consider metrics covering both the short term and projected long-term impact of the project.

Further information on innovation management will be included in the Data Management Plan and the iterations of the Dissemination and Exploitation Plans.

5.7 Conflict resolution

In the case of notable divergence from the objectives of one WP, a detailed plan of action will be established between the GA, the WP leader, and the contributors of the WP concerned. If important technical or financial re-orientations are required, decisions will be made during the GA meeting by consensus whenever possible, or if where necessary, and as a final resort, by a simple majority vote. All participants will be notified in advance of any proposed modifications to the work plan or budget allocations that are to be decided upon. Further conflict resolution measures including arbitration are defined in the Consortium Agreement.

6 Annexes

6.1 Depositing public documents in Zenodo

Documents linked to the project in Zenodo will be automatically picked up by the continuous reporting system of the Funding and Portal System, this will streamline the reporting process. In addition, this will guarantee a permanent record of the project output and generate DOIs.

In order to deposit and link documents to AtlantECO, please follow the steps below:

1. [Create an account](#) or [log in](#) (this can be done using your ORCID ID):

2. Select “Upload”

3. Select “New Upload”

The screenshot shows the Zenodo user dashboard for 'atlanteco@szn.it'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'zenodo', a search bar, and links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. Below this, a secondary search bar is present. A prominent green button labeled 'New Upload' is circled in pink. The main content area displays a list of uploads, including 'AtlantECO Overview and Work Packages presentations' and 'AtlantECO - Atlantic Ecosystems Assessment, Forecasting & Sustainability'. A pagination control at the bottom shows page 1 of 1.

4. In “Communities” type in or select AtlantECO

The screenshot shows the 'New upload' page in Zenodo. At the top, there are buttons for 'Delete', 'Save', and 'Publish'. The main heading is 'New upload', followed by instructions: '(i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star). (ii) Press “Save” to save your upload for editing later. (iii) When ready, press “Publish” to finalize and make your upload public.' Below the instructions is a file upload area with the text 'Drag and drop files here' and a 'Choose files' button. At the bottom, there is a 'Communities' section with a search bar and a 'recommended' dropdown menu. The 'Communities' label is circled in pink.

5. In section “Funding” select “EU” and “AtlantECO”

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